

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR

LEA

D3.3 LEA PPI Needs Analysis Report

15.2.2019

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 779803

AJUNTAMENT DE
VILADECANS

D3.3. LEA Needs Analysis Report

Project acronym: LEA

Project title: Learning Technology Accelerator

Grant Agreement number: 779803

Coordinator: Jyvaskylan Yliopisto

Project co-funded by the European Commission,
H2020

Funding Scheme: H2020-ICT-2017-1

Due date of deliverable:	31.10.2018
Actual submission date:	15.2.2019
Start date of the project:	March 1,2018
Project duration:	24 months

Workpackage	WP3
Task(s)	T3.3.
Lead beneficiary	University of Oulu
Editor/ authors	Markku Lang, Rita Freudenberg
Quality reviewers	LEA Procurers, JYU

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. Introduction

This report contains the cross border needs of the Buyers group for the future PPI of STEM PLE:s and is to be considered the first baseline of the PPI preparations. Based upon these needs the PPI preparation of the open market consultation will be held. A second report will be produced in M 14 using the same methodology in order to map the needs/ demands of LEA partners to prepare a PCP within the framework of LEA and will be a cross task with WP5.

"...biggest challenge faced by innovative companies in Europe is not to find funding for R&I but to find a first customer. The challenge is to facilitate access of innovative companies to the market by removing barriers to Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and Public Procurement of Innovative solutions (PPI) in Europe"

Balancing our needs workshop methodology (BON) was designed to highlight and to make students, teachers and European procurer expert board needs and demands visible and understandable for suppliers. This research-based design approach, developed by the Learning Environments research group in Media Lab Helsinki, is now used in LEA-project as a BON.

This design approach has been successfully used to design digital tools for learning and now it was used in need balancing workshops with living labs in 5 different countries and municipalities in LEA- project (*Ajuntament de Viladecans Spain, Citta di Torino Italy, Gothenburg Region Sweden,*

Konnevesi municipality Finland, Ministerium der Finanzen Sachsen Anhalt Germany and Municipio de Braga Portugal)

Methodology of LEA Needs Analysis has used features of The Future Classroom Toolkit¹ (based on design tools created by Aalto University). This set of tools enables teachers, school leaders, education policy makers and technology suppliers to create and implement Future Classroom Scenarios, which can be used as description of needs also in different procurement processes. Value of needs can also be balanced with the help of the same tools used in Future Classroom Toolkit.

Based upon the pathway of procurement and the PCP definition, the LEA consortium developed an exploratory analysis including needs identification and analysis of commercial solutions for the identified challenge of an increased demand of personalized learning. The needs of the procurers were analyzed and an innovation gap of PLE solutions in STEM for primary and secondary Education in Europe was discovered.

Here is a short highlighted summary of this need and market analysis which was delivering background data for needs analysis workshops in LEA.

These are the quantity indicators from the needs analysis:

- Clear view from 7 procurers (6 member states) representing hundreds of teachers and thousands of students.
- 300 teachers EU wide have given input to our surveys during 3 different stages
- Input from 24 organisations procuring and developing Education EU wide using surveys (European Procurement Expert Board, EPEB)

¹ <http://fcl.eun.org/toolkit>

- 560 students from Primary and Secondary school have been involved and discussed their vision about PLE and the future technology solutions for STEM
- 6 workshops in 6 countries with 100 teachers to discuss future of PLE and their identified needs
- Large group of STEM teachers (200) in a workshop in Brussels representing all EU member states

2 Personal Learning Environments (PLEs)

2.1. Personalised learning environment definitions

There are three important characteristics for a PLE to be used and developed that are different from Learning Management Systems (LMS) (Rodríguez Ilera, Rubio, Galván, & Barberà, 2014):

- **privacy**, referring to the student's control over their own publications,
- **feeling of ownership**, referring more to the ability to take decisions by the student to manage and use their own space (intangible elements such as control of learning objectives, content,...) than to control the technology used (Buchem, 2012),
- and **permanence**, concerning to the use of the personal space and learning records of the student throughout time (Olivier & Liber, 2001).

At this point, the role of teachers working with PLEs needs to be considered. According to Shaikh and Khoja (2011), there are five teachers' roles in PLE settings, which correspond with 5 kinds of tasks:

- Planning and design: setting up students' PLEs, designing learning activities, creating learning spaces, etc.
- Instruction and learning: mentoring, teaching and learning, information storage, motivation, etc.
- Communication and interaction: managing interactions, encourage peer learning, fostering learning and setting climate for learning, etc.
- Management and administration: responding to students' expectations, channelizing spaces of communication and voluntary participation, motivation and learning needs of students, etc.
- Use of technology: technical knowledge of support services, social computing applications, open access and proprietary software, data analysis, etc.

Figure 1: Components of the PLE. Source: Wheeler (2009).

A PLE develops, evolves and is shaped throughout life, depending on individual development and learning. The PLE ought to be supporting and controlling the whole Lifelong Learning Process and give the individual skills to create specific portfolios out of the experiences, creations and curations of the learning process (Leone, S. 2013).

The main feature of PLE is to support learning on lifelong basis. That means a challenge for the industry to serve a platform, which doesn't drop the users out during the lifelong learning process. It means different kind of business models connected to one platform.

2.2. Innovation in Personalised Learning

During the IMAILE project (www.imaile.eu), the innovative PLE technology/solutions were designed to meet the following requirements:

- Support to teachers and students in primary/ secondary education within Science, Math and Technology
- Reduce the planning hours for the teachers
- Support all students to reach their goals in a personalized way (gifted and with special needs)
- Create more 1 to 1 meetings between teacher and student in the classroom
- Increase the motivation to learn for our students using creative and collaborative learning methods in a personalized way
- Create a real shift from teacher centered learning to student centered learning (research shows that lessons in math and science still is mostly teacher-centered, with few opportunities for the students to have influence on their own learning and using digital tool).
- Be applicable to all devices (not fully BYOD concept, but our solution should be a tool that replicates the students' personal devices) and to all learning styles (tactile , visual auditory)
- Positive effect and reduce the numbers of early drop outs

By introducing this solution already in primary school we also expect this PLE to follow the student into Upper Secondary school and Higher education as a long term identity collected in a European Digital Portfolio. In IMAILE-project we chose to develop the PLE within STEM but the framework should be applicable on any other topic.

In the technology, this means several new features for the platform. The signing up process needs to flow. For single-sign-on, any service should open access to the PLE. The user profile should have personalizing features

like social media tools and add or edit profile information including social media.

The dashboard should have at least information and tools like calendar overview modules, that show next events, new activities from groups, overview of all user activities, list of all courses for a student, block for broadcasting news for all, social score (the more active the higher social score), full calendar overview, access to Course Builder tools (only Teachers). The teachers ought to build courses from templates and from any media or files. Building should be drag and drop based.

The score data from the tests, assignments and other work need to be collected, analysed and prepared easily to teachers, students and parents. The teachers and the students also need tools for recording the live lessons or other events for later use. This challenges the profile of the cloud storage space. The best option for the lifelong learner is unlimited storage space. One main feature for the primary and secondary PLE is the interaction with the parents. The parents need to access the platform to follow their children's work and achievements.

Also from the parent's point of view, the school needs to bring messages, their children's schedule, grades and credits, tests, attendance, support, and other basic information. The information about common questions like contact information, printouts, surveys, other announcements, study guidance and annual planning is also needed. The parents need to know about the attendances of their children and for example notify their absence. A student ought to collect all his/her activities under the same platform. The school work, free time activities and hobbies can be used as a platform for both formal and informal learning.

2.3 General Trends in Technology Enhanced Learning in 2018

Evaluation of trends in Technology enhanced learning (Cloud Computing, MOOC, OER, BYOD, Blended Learning, Gamification, Learning Analytics, E-Mentoring, Lifelong Learning), usability and the user Interface for PLE are the key elements for requirement specification for PLE 2018.

After analysing trends and scenarios, we found that cloud-based services include a wide range of increasingly powerful tools for almost any platform a user might choose, or any task a user might need to do. There are examples that with Cloud Computing teachers can track student grades and progress, create standard-aligned lesson plans, and generate analytics and reports.

With OER teacher can, for example, browse online photo galleries, select appropriately licensed images and use them as a learning resource. The advantages of OER extend beyond remixing existing resources. PLE with interface for shared educational resources saves time, since educators do not need to generate components from scratch. Learners also have the benefit of being able to customize their learning experiences with OER

A PLE should be independent of the operating system and be used with different devices. Perhaps the easiest way to make PLE as a cross platform service is to use techniques which support all devices (tablets, smartphones, desktops and laptops). HTML 5 is a recommended mark-up language.

The possibility of students easily accessing resources about any topic, combined with the presence of a PLE guiding their activity towards the learning goal, gives highly valuable meaning and resource to the face-to-face time. The PLE may serve as the ideal mediator to provide the right scaffolding, so that activities of higher cognitive load can be addressed in face-to-face sessions.

Gamification includes the use of game mechanics. Game mechanics can be effectively used in Learning Environments. With gamification, a PLE is getting a positive effect and becomes rewarding, dynamic, surprising,

motivating, supports collaboration and ownership, shows learners progression, time frame and level.

Learning analytics allows to capture a more detailed model of the students and their experiences within a learning environment. Data availability offers the possibility of re-thinking how experiences are approached and designed. New scenarios and strategies must now be considered based on the fact that designers and instructors will have detailed observations almost instantaneously. One of main consequences of collecting a detailed profile of how students behave in a learning environment is the possibility to provide a high degree of personalization.

Thus, analytics can be considered as one of the main forces that shape PLEs. In a data-rich environment, a PLE can be considered as an entity that mediates between a comprehensive set of resources and actions and the needs of a student, when trying to reach a specific goal.

If a virtual avatar (online assistant virtual teacher) has the possibility to use learning analytics and mentoring tools, it can provide an ideal learning assistant service to observe and foster self-regulated learning. A PLE is not only useful for the formal education in primary and secondary schools, it can be used in Informal Learning and in Non-Formal Learning as well, and since the usage of a PLE has no time limits, so LLL (Lifelong learning) should also be taking into consideration.

User interface design (UID) is the design with the focus on the usability, user's experience and interaction. The goal of user interface design is to make the user's interaction as simple and efficient as possible, in terms of accomplishing user goals—what is often called user-centered design. Good user interface design facilitates finishing the task at hand without drawing unnecessary attention to it. Graphic design may be utilized to support its usability, influencing how the user performs certain interactions and improving the aesthetic appeal of the design.

2. LEA Needs Analysis Methodology

When we implement digital technologies or transform school culture, there is a need for schools and school leaders to identify which improvements they actually want to achieve and which tools and methods should be used.

LEA Needs Analysis Methodology was used to identify:

- i) demands of public sector with procurers & learntech experts (This group was called the “European Procurement Experts Board” (EPEB))**
- ii) needs of public sector with end users (schools, teachers, students)**

2.1 Stakeholders of the LEA Needs Analysis

Overall, the following stakeholders were involved in the LEA Needs Analysis:

- 7 procurers (6 member states) representing hundreds of teachers and thousands of students.
- 300 teachers EU wide have given input to our surveys during 3 different stages
- Input from 24 organisations procuring and developing Education EU wide using surveys (European Procurement Expert Board, EPEB)
- 560 students from Primary and Secondary school have been involved and discussed their vision about PLE and the future technology solutions for STEM
- 6 Balancing Our Needs workshops in 6 countries with 100 teachers to discuss future of PLE and their identified needs
- Large group of STEM teachers (200) in a workshop in Brussels representing all EU member states

European Procurement Expert Board (EPEB)

European Procurement Expert Board (24 organisations) included representatives of seven procurer organisations in 6 countries (Finland,

Sweden, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Hungary). These experts have been working closely together with the schools in the respective countries and therefore have an understanding of both the needs of the procurement (municipalities, cities, states) as well as the end users within the schools. The EPEB also consisted learning technology experts and researchers studying IT pedagogy, future technologies etc. In addition, the EPEB included experts of innovation procurement procedures and methodologies - however, their involvement was only assisting in the work conducted..

LEA School Labs

Each Procuring country within the LEA project also conducted so called 'LEA School Labs' activities (BON workshops) in each LEA procuring country. This included collecting answers to LEA needs analysis questionnaire as well as organising the workshops described below. Further information on LEA School Labs can be read from deliverables D2.1. LEA Baseline as well as D4.4. Trainings developed to accelerate the dialogue between Supply & Demand.

2.2 Balancing our Needs Workshop Methodology

Users usually have difficulties with the level of needed quality and preparedness when participating in needs analysis processes. In the LEA Needs Analysis, we use Balancing Our Needs (BON) methodology. It starts with trends to assure that the needs analysis is future orientated enough. This way, sustainability (green footprint) is taken into account and it gives also an overview and inspiration of the theme.

When comparing different features of a product to be designed, you want to know which of these features are most important and relevant for the

users and why. The goal of the BON workshop is to reveal these features of a PLE.

A BON workshop gives results in three categories. First you get the list of the most important features wanted in a PLE. From that list, we then create minimum requirements. These may be divided into minimum requirements in different countries. These results are the base for scenarios created to enlighten and describe the desired workflow possible with a new and innovative PLE.

By using scenarios, we give to the suppliers a clear, but open vision about what is needed. Scenarios are highly usable in innovative procurement, because they are inspiring, but at the same time telling clearly with a concrete example, what the minimum requirements are. At the same time, it provides an effective tool for evaluating different alternatives.

The needs analysis workshops were designed by OU and OVGU. European procurer expert board (EPEB) had a Balancing our Needs workshop in Halmstad in June 2018.

Figure 2: LEA Scenario creation workshop with EPEB in Halmstad, June 2018

The workshop also included a scenario writing session. In October 2018, schools in six countries performed workshops where students were comparing pretensions, watching inspiring videos of learning scenarios and creating demands for PLE. In these workshops, also included was a mapping of the limitations in infrastructure and technology, which are hindering or stopping the use of technology or Personal Learning Environments.

Students were asked to draw one vertical and one horizontal line to the center of a sheet of paper and write on the left upper corner "POSSIBILITIES", right upper corner "CHALLENGES", left bottom corner "TECHNOLOGIES" and on the right bottom corner "SPACES". After that, each group got a link to one of the learning Scenarios. Each group

watched the video of their own Learning Scenario from mobile phones, computers etc. The questions they had to answer were the following:

- What technologies (software, hardware) could now be used in this learning scenario?
- What spaces (indoor, outdoor, virtual) could be used in this learning scenario?
- Which benefits or possibilities this learning scenario gives to students?
- What kind of challenges does your school have for this learning scenario? Does infrastructure or culture (timetable, workflow, teachers skills) make it impossible to fulfill?

Figure 3: Example whiteboard from BON Workshop in Germany, Autumn 2018

The students came up with several suggestions of what kind of technology could be used in the learning scenarios, including voice control systems, laptops, mobiles with special apps, cameras and computers in general.

Regarding the spaces where the scenarios could be used, the students consider all spaces as possible places for learning: at home or in school, in the garden, playground or other public and private places, indoors and outdoors. That shows that for the students, learning can take place everywhere and that they are familiar enough with several technological devices to know that they can be used in many places.

The possibilities and benefits students see from the various learning scenarios are a list of possible activities, like drawing, doing presentations, taking pictures etc. and they also say that these kind of projects are a funnier way to learn.

But the students are also very sensitive to the challenges their schools are facing when using these kind of learning scenarios. They know the basic needs, like being able to connect to the internet, having money to buy the technology, electrical power and the ability to use the software.

2.3 Scenario methodology in BON Workshops

"Scenarios are innovative and challenging ideas of what learning and teaching could be."

Scenarios were used in the IMAILE- project to have a view of the situation and a perspective to near future including trends in technology and in education. Different scenarios doesn't mean different alternatives. In the process of the IMAILE project, different scenarios (teachers, students and European procurer expert board) were complementing each other so that

the PCP process could have the broadest possible viewpoint and best information for making needs analysis and requirements specification.

With the help of scenarios created 2015 in IMAILE, we can evaluate needed features to PLE now in the PPI phase of LEA also. Here are key sentences from these different scenarios. Scenarios are based on **State of the Art in Personal Learning Environments**². Some words are in bold to indicate one feature of a PLE:

- Teachers' work has become **easier** and learning processes have become **more transparent**.
- My teacher said that the PLE will be my **teaching assistant** and my virtual mother from now on.
- Petri has guided me in **when and how** I should work.
- A lot of things I would certainly have forgotten, if Petri was not there **reminding** and **guiding** me.
- **My first task** was to tell to Petri my timetable.
- One of the best things in PLE has been the fact that I can **travel in time**.
- Automatic time lining has helped me especially in **preparing** for exams.
- On a **parallel** timeline I have been able to see lessons, guidance of my teachers, comments and questions.
- Working with PLE gives you **credits and points**.
- If we are having a **team work**, we can send a time capsule of our group or team.
- As a senior student I have also been able to study courses in **other schools**.
- I used my PLE and the **employer** saw that I have been working hard at school and that I can express myself in many ways

² Lang, M. Lounaskorpi, P. Pardo, A

- PLE can be opened and edited using **any device** that is online and has a web browser.
- Through the use of PLE teachers have noticed that students are more active and **engaged in designing** their own learning strategies.
- PLE has also been supporting better **contact** between student and teachers.

The process started by analyzing key sentences of previous scenarios. The scenarios were analyzed and reformed to 23 different pretensions. These pretensions were used to get a helicopter view over the educational and learning landscape before the workshops in living labs, teachers and European procurer expert board of the LEA- project have been held.

Which one of these features of PLE (Personal Learning Environment) is more important for you?

1. *To be able to work offline and online seamlessly*
2. *To use any device (BYOD, Bring Your Own Device)*
3. *To use it in school and in free time*
4. *To that teacher can control what is happening in classroom*
5. *To help teachers in assessment*
6. *To collaborate easier*
7. *To be connected with parents*
8. *To be connected with students*
9. *To be connected with society*
10. *To have access to digital content and curricula*
11. *To help teachers with technology*
12. *Lifelong learning*
13. *To manage knowledge*
14. *To personalisation*

15. *To collect your work (a visual diary) and to show your ideas*
16. *To help succeeding in school*
17. *To help teacher in planning teaching*
18. *To help studying and to control your studies*
19. *To help teacher to save time*
20. *To help students to reach their goals*
21. *To help with Science, Math and Technology*
22. *To help teachers to give students more time to study*
23. *To help teachers to be more creative and more collaborative*

LEA states that there needs to be a distinction between needs and demand and we focus on demand driven innovations with early involvement of end users in the development process. These workshop methodologies and results will be presented in LEA Roadmap as training material.

3. Results of the Needs Analysis

3.1 What are the detailed common needs of the procurers (students)?

In BON workshops for students were given over 15 000 votes. Most wanted and most important features of PLE for students are listed below. We used these features as pretensions, which were competing against each other's. In the right side you can see how many percent of other pretensions this pretension wins.

S	T		FIN	ITA	GER	SPA	POR	SWE	WIN %
1	1	To help students to reach their goals	58	57	52	72	61	67	61,20
2	2	To help succeeding in school	57	56	60	58	68	58	59,50
3	6	To help studying and to control your studies	54	61	56	62	68	55	59,30
4	7	To help teachers to give students more time to study	55	61	47	58	51	51	53,80
5	12	To collaborate easier	55	52	56	50	52	50	52,50
6	13	To be able to work offline and online seamlessly	51	38	56	54	53	60	52,00
7		To manage knowledge	50	51	44	52	61	53	51,80
8	9	To be connected with students	47	56	46	51	58	53	51,00
9	4	To have access to digital content and curricula	51	44	49	51	53	57	50,80
10		To help with Science, Math and Technology	42	58	47	56	54	46	50,50
11		Lifelong learning	54	45	56	38	62	42	49,80
12	3	To help teachers to be more creative and more collaborative	55	46	38	57	50	47	48,80
13		To that teacher can control what is	49	50	47	49	42	55	48,70

		happening in classroom							
14	11	To collect your work (a visual diary) and to show your ideas	53	47	51	42	50	48	48,50

Table 1: Results; Top 14 pretension of 23 (in detailed common needs of the students). T- column shows the results of teachers pair wise comparison.

BON starts with a pairwise comparison of two randomly selected pretensions and an analysis of the results of that. Pairwise comparison makes manipulation, or “gaming,” of results difficult, because respondents cannot choose which pairs they will see; instead, this choice is made by the tool.

Pairwise comparison requires respondents to prioritize items. Because the respondent must select one of two pretensions from each pair, he/she is prevented from simply saying that she likes (or dislikes) every option equally strongly. This feature is particularly valuable in policy and planning contexts.

As can be seen in table 1, students in different countries (Finland, Italy, Spain, Portugal and Sweden) have quite similar thoughts in pairwise comparison. The numbers represent the percentage how often this pretension will win against others in pair comparison. If an opinion in a country differs from average over 5 %, it is colored in red (stronger meaning for this country) or blue (weaker meaning for this country).

In each country, students are thinking that a PLE should help students to reach their goals. The importance of this feature seems to be really highly valued in Spain and in Sweden where the difference to the average is over 5%.

Explanations of students views on table 1 (order of importance to them):

1. “To help students to reach their goals” can be seen as an indicator for the need of self regulation, because the pretension mentions “their goals”. Let students set their own goals seems to be the most important challenge to a PLE at the moment. In each country

2. “To help succeeding in school” seems also to be really important, but this pretension is quite obvious and has no significant input to the needs analysis.

The next important feature for PLE according to the students is

3. “To help studying and to control your studies”. This seems to be a really important feature for students in Portugal. What does it mean, if students need a PLE to help in studies (studying) and to control your studies?

We can expect that the PLE should then enable for example the monitoring of user behavior and performance in the solution. It should also continuously analyze the behavior and performance of each individual student to identify preferred learning styles, learning content and learning activities. It should provide recommendations to teachers and students on how to adjust the learning path of each individual student to fit their identified preferences

PLE should provide the possibility for students to review the results of the analysis regarding their learning preferences to enable the self-reflection on the own learning process

PLE should Integrate and provide easy access to external sources for learning content. Provide support of informal learning by allowing students to set their own learning goals and learning paths for topics of their interest outside of the curriculum

PLE should provide an Intelligent Tutoring System that supports students in their creation of own learning goals and learning paths by suggesting topics, content and activities based on the analysis of their learning preferences. Provide the possibility to schedule online meetings with the teachers for students, parents and European procurer expert board as a virtual version of office hours.

Motivation is also important point of view in helping students to reach their goals. PLE should perhaps provide badges and badge libraries as well as leaderboards to enable the gamification of learning for extra boost of motivation.

4. ***“To help teachers to give students more time to study”*** is the next most valuable pretension, which provides a big role for some new innovations. Students in Italy are respecting this feature significantly more than students in other countries.

If a PLE provides a way to identify early signs for drop-outs e.g. through the analysis of activities in the system, completion of assignments, and performance, it would definitely save teachers time for students. If the PLE provides a smart parent support system and gives guidance for parents with children underperforming or at risk of dropping out, it would also save teachers time.

The next valuable pretensions are

5. ***“To collaborate easier”*** and

6 ***“To be able to work offline and online seamlessly”***

To enable and support collaboration, the PLE must provide tools for the cooperation of students and teachers. (creation of interest or learning groups, setting group goals, having group calendars etc.) It should perhaps integrate social media functionalities from external providers. (sharing of materials and results through channels such as Facebook and Twitter) and it should use both asynchronous and synchronous communication channels

The PLE should also support community building and networking among students and teachers within the system. It should provide feedback functionalities. Teachers can give direct feedback regarding specific tasks, learning activities or assessments to groups; individuals and a student can give direct feedback to their educator and peers and even Artificial Intelligence (here perhaps an avatar) could give direct feedback to students.

The importance and success of pretension ***“To be able to work offline and online seamlessly”*** in this pair comparison is understandable because students are facing the need to have a freedom to choose where, when and how to work and how to collaborate with others.

Pretensions 7. ***“To manage knowledge”*** and 9. ***“To have access to digital content and curricula”*** can be seen as the need to take good control of learning resources. The PLE should provide a material storage solution, which helps to organize and to reorganize content. Created materials (Learning Objects, Essays etc.) should be shared to peers and the PLE should support open educational resources (OER) and a variety of learning

object repositories (LOR). Created materials (Learning Objects, Essays etc.) could also be shared through external systems (e.g. Facebook, Twitter etc.).

Faster usability and better accessibility follows high quality of authoring and editing tools. A PLE should support a wide range of media files (which file formats are supported). It should also have an effective search function and should use tags to connect materials to specific skill and knowledge levels.

8. **"To be connected with students"** can be seen as a supporting pretension for the pretension 6. **"To be able to work offline and online seamlessly"** and 11. **"Lifelong Learning"** can be seen as a signal of high importance of connection between teacher and student and the usability, accessibility and the quality needed in user interface.

A PLE should have a really easy and quick access, perhaps face recognition or similar. The UI should keep its identity and usability with the use of different browsers, devices and operating systems. The PLE should be automatically scaled to fit the students skills & competencies.

A really important finding in pair comparison is that because pretension 10. **"To help with Science, Math and Technology"** barely gets over 50 % wins according to the average student in Europe, the previous assumption that the need for a PLE is significant in STEM subjects, seems to be wrong or at least not among the most important features. PLEs should not be subject oriented according to the opinions of students.

3.2 What are the detailed common needs of the procurers (teachers)?

		FIN	POR	SWE	WI N %
1	To help students to reach their goals	67	71	71	69,7
2	To help succeeding in school	54	65	85	68,0
3	To help teachers to be more creative and more collaborative	68	68	50	62,0
4	To have access to digital content and curricula	63	49	63	58,3
5	To help teacher in planning teaching	56	57	61	58,0
6	To help studying and to control your studies	57	57	50	54,7
7	To help teachers to give students more time to study	59	49	50	52,7
8	Personalisation	68	45	44	52,3
9	To be connected with students	51	60	45	52,0

10	To use any device (BYOD, Bring Your Own Device)	59	38	59	52,0
11	To collect your work (a visual diary) and to show your ideas	53	48	50	50,3
12	To collaborate easier	58	63	13	44,7
13	To be able to work offline and online seamlessly	53	33	41	42,3
14	To use it in school and in free time	53	13	25	30,3

Table 2: Results; Top 14 pretension of 23 (in detailed common needs of the teachers). Pretensions in bold face are not existing in the top 14 pretensions of the students.

Because a PLE is used and orchestrated by students and teachers, it is good to compare the differences of needs between these two groups. In Table 2 teachers pairwise comparison shows that the two pretensions 1. **“To help students to reach their goals”** and 2. **“To help succeeding in school”** are equally evaluated by both groups. But more interesting is number 3. **“To help teachers to be more creative and more collaborative”**, which indicates big hopes teachers have for PLE.

The same trend seems to be continuing in the top 14 pretensions of teachers which students don’t see so important. 5. **“To help teacher in planning teaching”**, 6. **“Personalisation”**, 10. **“To use any device (BYOD, Bring Your Own Device)”**, 14. **“To use it in school and in free time”**.

These pretensions teachers are seeing important in PLE are features which support Blended Learning in different models and phases. This represents the innovative approach of teachers, based on their education and knowledge of trends in Education. That is something students, of course, don't have and that's why these needs/features of PLE are missing on their list.

When a PLE supports Blended Learning, it provides eg. functionalities of self-evaluation, enables continuous evaluation, provides tutoring and avatars which have "ability" to use the path of learners data for e-mentoring purposes, provides guidance to students, provides automated certificates or badges for students, provides rewarding, surprising and motivating; and makes teachers work easier in multiple ways.

There seem to be significant differences also between teachers and school culture in different countries. For example 2. **"To help succeeding in school"** seems overwhelmingly important for teachers in Sweden, but the most important feature for teachers in Finland and in Portugal is 3. **"To help teachers to be more creative and more collaborative"**.

Teachers in Finland need features which are helping teachers to give students more time to study, in personalisation, in the use of any device, in collaborating, to work offline and online and in the use it in school and in free time. Teachers in Portugal need features from a PLE which helps being connected with students and to collaborate with them easier. These features seem not be in the top of 14 list for Swedish teachers.

Teachers in Portugal think that the use of any device (BYOD, Bring Your Own Device) is not a relevant feature or should not be on a feature list for PLE. Teachers in Finland and Sweden are instead thinking the opposite way.

This may have several different explanations. Perhaps in Portugal, in these schools at least, every student has a device provided by school. In turn in Sweden and in Finland teachers have a bigger need and enthusiasm for blended learning, where using your own device and studying in different places is in the core of pedagogy.

Teachers also want to be more creative and more collaborative, which shows the need for some new features for a PLE. This innovative approach teachers have is based on their education and knowledge of trends in Education.

Teachers in Finland need features which are helping teachers to give students more time to study, for personalisation, the use of any device, collaborating, to work offline and online and to use the system in school and in free time. Teachers in Portugal need features in a PLE which helps being connected with students and to collaborate with them easier. These features seems not be in the top of 14 list for Swedish teachers.

BON workshops are showing that PLE plays important role in the formation of the learning landscape of the 21st century education. Many features of described PLE are already existing, but not composed in one solution for learning and teaching purposes. For example, learning analytics is already being used in different learning platforms, but not for decreasing student dropouts, maximizing engagement, increasing self-reflection, supporting diversity, reducing the complexity of learning design, etc.

3.3 Scenarios of European PLE Needs

The European procurer expert board had a Balancing Our Needs workshop in Halmstad in June 2018. The workshop also included a scenario writing session. Results in pairwise comparison bring out (without surprise), that a

PLE should support all students to reach their goals. European procurer expert board think like teachers that the use of creative and collaborative learning methods in a personalized way is a really important activity for teachers and for students.

Scenario European Procurers Expert Board (EPEB)

The use of a PLE has assisted parents to follow their children's studying and schooling, but students still have room for their own learning and parents don't know everything they do. They still share the results of their schoolwork in person and talk to each other. Routine communication between home and school (events, absences, public notices, etc.) is taking place on other communication tools, but the PLE gives a whole new perspective for monitoring the study-processes by the students. PLEs are used for communication between students who live farther away from each other to work together.

First Impressions

"I do not know quite exactly if this is the result the use of PLE, but last year the teachers' days of sick leave started after a long time to fall. Because each student and teacher can now use their personal device in their work, we are starting to get considerable savings in IT management revenues. Distribution of teaching and learning materials is also now with PLE simplified and more straightforward."

Visualization

"The visualized path of learning processes has helped students and teachers to work more closely in direction of the objectives. With a better management of time and resources, PLE has enabled to focus on the

future competences. With the help of visualizations we have been able to focus on the semantic memory and the children as well as adults are now beginning to understand larger entities. Utilization of the current computer based learning technologies have increased students' motivation for studying, and teachers have had more time for supporting learning and for designing their teaching."

Because PLE is using cleverly ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, we are aware better all the time of what is happening in schools right up to the individual level. Learning assistance and the differentiation upwards has become possible. In this way, each student is receiving personalised education on their own level.

BYOD

Because of the PLE, we are aware better all the time of what is happening in schools right up to the individual level. Learning assistance and the differentiation upwards has become possible. In this way, each student is receiving appropriate education on their own level. We have also now been able to take full advantage of different mobile devices. The students are using their personal devices.

The PLE is supporting cloud-based services and minimizes the risk by observing the data privacy regulations and information security.

Scenario (Teacher)

Through the use of the PLE, teachers have noticed that students are more active and engaged in designing their own learning strategies. The PLE has also been supporting better contact between student and teachers. Teaching and learning processes are now less teacher-centered. The PLE

has a surprising important role in the formation of learning landscape of the 21st century education.

First Impressions

I have a long time been waiting for a tool that would help me in supporting learning processes of my students and which also facilitates my work to such an extent that I could focus more on my students. When PLE was presented to our school for the first time, I understood that this might be the solution I had been longing for. We tested the solution in our school lab for 3 months.

Blended Learning

I am a physics teacher in our secondary school and today just before the beginning of the lesson I had a quick look to the PLE. I was interested, how my students had understood after their own research the concepts of absorbing and releasing energy. I opened their own physics timeline and I realized immediately that the the concept of energy releasing was still little unclear - in some extent. I exported with one click the questions my students had made about the topic to a one video clip, and threw myself on the role as an external expert during the lesson.

We had quite a lot of fun when I was trying to answer these questions. One question remained unanswered and we decided to make a shared mind map about this topic. We saved the mind map and every one made a time capsule of their own and added into it a reminder to their timeline. We shall work with it in September, but from a different perspective.

Personalized learning

We are going to receive tomorrow a new student here in our school. I watched today his learning processes in general, skills he have and I also looked at his student profile from PLE. I noticed an interesting thing. He is a hard working student but surprisingly often underperforming in tests. After looking the PLE I think I now know why this happened. I have good feeling about the meeting in the afternoon with him and his parents.

Sharing

I looked today how our teachers are working nowadays. I just have to wonder about the level of collaboration, co-planning and discussion. It's excellent, that teaching and design processes are happening today in teams. Making of the teaching materials and sharing it is so easy that it leaves more time for all of us.

Content creation

Next month I shall have an e-learning course to support the blended learning in my class. I shall create the learning path to my students in PLE course builder. The readymade templates help me to create the path and I only drag and drop the files and other materials in the visualized learning path. I use e-books, OER materials and my own documents (assignments, tests etc.) to create the combination to support individual learners.

Flipped classroom

For the next mathematic lesson I shall create a short video as a teaser to the students. With PLE's video/screen capture recorder I shall combine my Power point slides with my voice and create SOOC (Short Open Online Course) on the topic. I will send the link to my students via PLE as a quick message to the social media service, where he/she is active at the time. I also will give them a problem to think for the next lesson combined video recording. I also link the e-book chapter as flipped material for the students to prepare the lesson.

Parent collaboration

I send quick messages to parents to their emails and mobile phones as an sms. I also indicate the absence of students and get the explanation from the parents. In PLE dashboard is always live schedule for everyone to see. Individual students and parents can see information about the tests, homework, exams and other information connected to their dependent.

Evaluation

For the term evaluation I just collect the progress information from each student in the PLE. All the assignments, tests, exams and other work has been graded or evaluated by the system and can be used by the teacher. The self evaluation tool of the system gives also the students grab on their development and make their self esteem stronger..

Scenario (Student)

The PLE (Personal Learning Environment) has proven to be a significant factor to that a school is nowadays in an interesting, engaging and suitable way a challenging place. Teachers' work has become easier and learning processes have become more transparent. Co-design and PCP processes have enabled a rapid change in school culture because all stakeholders

have been brought into these participatory design processes. Here is short scenario how PLE has helped one student in primary school and in secondary school.

First impressions

I remember very well when PLE was introduced to me for the first time . My teacher said that the PLE will be my teaching assistant and my virtual tutor from now on. First i had the chance to shape the personality and character of my teaching assistant (avatar). I named him as Petri. Petri started to come out from time to time to ask questions and to give advices. Petri has guided me in when and how I should work. A lot of things I would certainly have forgotten, if Petri was not reminding and guiding me.

My first task was to tell to Petri what kind of timetable i have. In this way Petri became aware of what and when should I study. I told to Petri also mine own hobbies and schedules. I chose in the beginning my teachers from the list of our teachers. Now I was able to show questions to them and to do tasks assigned to me.

At first I had hardly no management skills and I didn't know how long it would take me to read or write certain assignments. Petri was measuring my reading and writing speed and he could tell pretty accurately if I was behind on my schedule. I got points and badges when my writing speed got better and Petri suggested typewriting exercises to develop myself. All the students reading and writing skills as well as concentration skills were documented by Petri and my teacher got the information of my development. Petri was functioning as a FitBit of learning reminding me about my daily exercises, assignments and nagging if it thought I was behind my schedule.

Time travelling/Setting own goals or achievements

One of the best things in PLE has been the fact that I can travel in time. I have been able to look afterwards what, how and when I have been working with. I have also created many time capsules. Time capsule is a goal or a dream that is locked and can be opened on a specific date. I have written many goals for what I want to learn and achieve. I am now eighteen years old and last week I opened a time capsule which was locked and sent to the future when I was in the third grade. I was 10 years old then. I could read that at the age of eighteen I would like to play soccer in the best team of our city. It's funny that I just made a contract with the best team in our city, but in ice hockey. Most of time capsules I have sent to future have been locked for a considerably short time. Sometimes even just for a week.

Automatic timelining has helped me especially in preparing for exams. On a parallel timeline I have been able to see lessons, guidance of my teachers, comments and questions. This has helped me a great deal. I have e.g. looked videos about difficult topics again and again. There are hundreds of video clips on my timeline because I remember things better from videos than images. Some of my friends have their timeline full of drawings and notes. I have also quite a lot mind maps there. I prefer to use digital pen for making mind maps and of course in mathematics, physics and chemistry. OCR has sometimes been a handy feature, but usually I use virtual keyboard on my tablet. Sometimes I have used speech recognition and sometimes I have been recording audio notes.

Levels

Working with PLE gives you credits and points. I have got points from regularity, good planning, solving difficult problems, helping others, etc. When you have enough points you can get access from one level to next. I just achieved the next level of study physics. I got access to purple level. It is the best one.

Working together

I have also some common material together with my friends. We can also send a time capsule of our group or team. Usually we have used workflow recording feature in PLE and we have also recorded a short clip what we did, did we have any difficulties and what shall we do next. This has been a handy feature and we have watched or listened recordings with teachers comments, before starting to work again.

As a senior student I have also been able to study courses in other schools and it's all has nicely assembled to my timeline. I remember when I was teaching magic tricks to our group. I recorded some video guides and everyone had a small magician show in the end of the course. Some even asked other (really pro) magicians for good tips.

My friend Laura has special needs. It was good to see that the PLE and her virtual tutor was supporting her better, different way than me.

Portfolio

Last week I applied for a summer job and had a job interview. I used there my PLE to show my studies, badges, achievements and skills. Employer saw that I have been working hard at school and I can express myself in many ways and I can foreign languages as well. I got the job!

PLE can be opened and edited using any device that is online and has a web browser. It is good that I can also use it offline. Now I am finishing high school and I can have PLE as a portfolio with me. I will continue to use it in the future in my studies and after that in my work.

On top of the portfolio the PLE is making a public profile of me with all the assignments and evaluations. Profile of learning is the way to show the learning process and learning methods. It means that the student is motivated enough to add different kinds of assignments and processes of learning, that show what kind of learner he/she is and how he/she learns best. A classroom of students forms a group of profiles. The idea is that the students can evaluate each other's assignments and processes and encourage each other to learn more. This could be done anonymously or with real names. The teacher evaluates the assignments and processes of the students and gives feedback on learning.

Extra-curricular activities

I also have chances to follow my own interests, for example when I get ahead of the schedule, and as a senior student I have also been able to study courses in other schools. Both of these have nicely assembled to my timeline. As an example, I was teaching magic tricks to our group. I recorded some video guides and everyone made a small magic show in the end of the course.

3.4 Summarised needs in LEA procurer countries (EPEB)

In Braga (November 2018), the European procurer expert board were asked again about the needs for PLE in different countries. These experts had been the ones supervising the 'Balancing our needs' workshops in real

classroom environments in the Autumn of 2018 in the six countries. Needs were prioritised into two categories “MUST HAVE” and “NICE TO HAVE”.

In Sweden, it is indispensable that a PLE is used everywhere and with every operating system and device. It also has to be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with gamification principles. In the “NICE TO HAVE” category, Sweden likes that a PLE should save teachers time and recognize school dropouts. The PLE should also have open source language tools.

In Portugal, it is indispensable that a PLE must recognize early school dropouts, it must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with their learning goals. The PLE should also save teachers time and should be used everywhere and with every operating system and device.

In Finland, it is indispensable that a PLE is easy to use and motivates and supports students with their learning goals. The PLE must also save teachers time and should support the work with transversal / future skills.

In Spain, it is indispensable that a PLE supports students with their learning goals and saves teachers time with designing learning. It must also be easy to use and should recognize early school dropouts as well as should be used everywhere and support communication between teachers and parents. In Spain, it is also very crucial that PLE should come with ready-made content within.

The European procurer expert board is also more worried about students dropouts, so a PLE should reduce the numbers of early dropouts, help in personalisation and support student centered- and Lifelong learning.

The European procurer expert board got Learning Scenarios created 2015 in the IMAILE- project as a “template” to compare and to evaluate, and to make some updates to them. The Learning Scenarios below are updated from the view of the European procurer expert board, teachers and students.

4. Summary of LEA Needs Analysis

PLE Needs from LEA procurers can be summarised to following tables 3-8:

SPAIN

MUST HAVE	NICE TO HAVE
<p>PLE must support students with their learning goals.</p> <p>PLE must save teachers time with designing learning</p> <p>PLE must be easy to use.</p>	<p>PLE should early recognize school dropouts.</p> <p>PLE should be used everywhere and support communication between teachers and parents.</p>

SWEDEN

MUST HAVE	NICE TO HAVE
<p>PLE must be used everywhere and with every operating systems and devices.</p> <p>PLE must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with gamification principles</p>	<p>PLE should save teachers time and recognize school dropouts. PLE should have open source language inclusion.</p>

PORTUGAL

MUST HAVE	NICE TO HAVE
<p>PLE must early recognize school dropouts</p> <p>PLE must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with their learning goals</p>	<p>PLE should save teachers time and recognize school dropouts.</p> <p>PLE should be used everywhere and with every operating systems and devices.</p>

FINLAND

MUST HAVE	NICE TO HAVE
<p>PLE must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with their learning goals.</p> <p>PLE must save teachers time.</p>	<p>PLE should support to work with transversal / future skills.</p>

ITALY

MUST HAVE	NICE TO HAVE
<p>PLE must be ubiquitous and support the use of modern learning landscape</p> <p>PLE must support students to work together with transversal / future skills.</p>	<p>PLE should early recognize school dropouts.</p> <p>PLE should be easy to use and used everywhere</p>

Tables 3-8: Summarised LEA Needs from countries

5. LEA Recommendation on 10 Key Needs for PLEs

1. PLE supports creativity

The user Interface and how information architecture is structured in a PLE has a big influence to school culture and to the ways users are thinking about studying, teaching and schooling. Because the needs for collaboration and creativity have now raised to the most valuable and appreciated features of a PLE, design must focus on that.

PLE should save time of the teacher. It should save time for preparing lessons, evaluating lessons and during lessons to enable more time to 1-1 contact with students.

2. PLE has an innovative UID

User interface design (UID) is the design with the focus on the usability, user's experience and interaction. The goal of user interface design is to make the user's interaction as simple and efficient as possible. Visualizing information makes studying, understanding and learning more effective.

3. PLE is independent and connected

One device per student ratio is already a norm achieved in the Northern European countries, but not in all areas/schools in Europe. The PLE should be designed for devices that students already have. When designing, for example, a service like a PLE it is good to use a protocol which is as widely used and updated as possible. That's why HTML5 is a recommendation for markup languages at the moment. Connectivity and openness also creates independency and is really important for lifelong learning.

4. PLE boosts speed

The user interface, information architecture and programming of the PLE should be designed in the scope of usability and speed. The time of active use of the PLE should be as short as possible. It's not a preferable that the use of PLE increases screen time too much. Logging in should use modern technologies like face recognition to save time.

A PLE should be so easy and simple to use that no training is needed. When downloading commercial apps (e.g. Uber or Instagram or Wolt) to our smartphones - we just take it to use. It is so intuitive that we learn how to use it by using it.

5. PLE supports different models of Blended Learning

The virtual space for learning provided by a PLE is a powerful enhancer. The possibility of students accessing resources about any topic, combined with the presence of the PLE guiding their activity towards the goal of learning, renders the face-to-face time as yet another highly valuable resource that needs to be effectively used. The PLE may serve as the ideal mediator to provide the right scaffolding so that activities of higher cognitive load can be addressed in face-to-face sessions.

The PLE should support and motivate students to reach their learning goals through engaged participation. In the 21st century education, the students choose their own learning goals and learning preferences (e.g. textual, auditive, video content) and are actively responsible for building their own knowledge. The teacher's role is to mentor the process of each student's personal learning path. The solution learns from the student.

6. PLE uses learning analytics in an effective and innovative way

Learning analytics allow to capture a more detailed model of the students and their experience within a learning landscape. Data availability offers the possibility of re-thinking how experiences are approached and designed. One of the main consequences of collecting a detailed profile of how students behave in a learning environment is the possibility to provide a high degree of personalization. In a data-rich environment, a PLE can be considered as an entity that mediates between a comprehensive set of resources and actions and the needs of a student when trying to reach a specific goal.

7. PLE is a tool for Lifelong learning

A PLE is not only for the formal education in primary and secondary schools. A PLE can be used in Informal Learning and in Non-Formal Learning as well and the usage of a PLE has no time limits, so LLL (Lifelong learning) should also be taken into consideration.

8. PLE uses innovatively different game mechanics

Gamification includes the use of game mechanics. Game mechanics can be effectively used in Learning Environments. With gamification, a PLE is providing an positive effect, rewarding, supporting collaboration, dynamic, surprising, motivating, supporting ownership and showing learners progression, time frame and level.

9. PLE takes automated online assistance to the next level

If an virtual avatar (online assistant virtual teacher) has the possibility to use learning analytics and e-mentoring tools, it can provide a ideal learning assistant service to observe and foster self-regulated learning.

A PLE should notify students, teachers & parents when students have severe learning difficulties (or if they are performing well) and adaptively support the student before they reach critical challenges that could lead to a school drop-out.

10. PLE is using effectively and safely Cloud Computing

Cloud-based services are an effective and ergonomic way in offline-online work. When it is designed well, it gives the possibility to jump between offline and online work, even allows working in groups. There are examples that with Cloud Computing teachers can track student grades and progress, create standard-aligned lesson plans, and generate analytics and reports.

REFERENCES

Abrami, P. C., & Barrett, H. (2005). Directions for research and development on electronic portfolios. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology*, 31(3), 1-15. Are Personalized Learning Environments the Next Wave of K-12 Education Reform? In: Education issue papers series, American Institutes for Research, 2013.

Alharbi, M. T., Platt, A. & Al-Bayatti, A. H. (2013).

Personal Learning Environment. In: *International Journal for e-Learning Security (IJELS)*, Volume 3, Issues 1/2.

Attwell, G. (2007).

Personal Learning Environments - the future of eLearning? In: eLearning. Papers, Issue No.2. Quality in eLearning.

Attwell, G. 2010.

Working, learning and playing through Personal Learning Environments. The 1st PLE 2010 conference, Barcelona, Spain, 8–9 July 2010.

Azevedo, R. (2005a).

Computers as metacognitive tools for enhancing learning. Educational Psychologist (Special Issue on Computers as Metacognitive Tools for Enhancing Student Learning), 40(4), 193–197.

Bentley, T., & Miller, R. (2004).

Personalised learning: Creating the ingredients for system and society wide change . Melbourne: IARTV Incorporated Association of Registered Teachers of Victoria.

Bailey, J.Martin, N. (Eds).

Blended learning - implementation guide. 2013.

Bucheler T., Labhart N. & Rowland, B. (2010)

(Eds.) The ShanghAI Lectures 2009 Final Project Report, Artificial Intelligence Laboratory, University of Zurich

Buchem, I. (2012). Psychological Ownership and Personal Learning Environments. Do possession and control really matter? In The PLE Conference 2012. Aveiro, Portugal. Retrieved from <http://revistas.ua.pt/index.php/ple/article/viewFile/1437/1323>

Caldwell, G. Bilandzic, M. & Foth, M. (2012).

Towards visualising people's ecology of hybrid personal learning environments

Casta eda, L. Adell, . (toim.) 2011 .

Entornos personales de aprendi aje claves para el ecosistema educativo en red. Alcoy: Marfil. <http://www.um.es/ple/libro/>

Chatti, M. 2007. Personal environments loosely joined. Mohamed Amine Chatti's ongoing research on Knowledge and Learning blog, January 02,

Edquist, C., Zabala-Iturriagagoitia, J-M. 2012. Why Pre-Commercial Procurement is not Innovation Procurement. Centre for Innovation, Research and Competence in the Learning Economy (CIRCLE). Lund University.

European Commission (2006a) Pre - commercial Procurement. A missing link in the European innovation cycle. European Commission.

European Commission (2006b) Pre - commercial Procurement. Public sector needs as a driver of innovation. European Commission.

European Commission (2008) Pre - commercial Procurement: Driving innovation to ensure sustainable high quality public services in Europe. SEC(2007) 1668. Brussels.

Greene, J.A. Azevedo, R. (2010). Introduction The measurement of learner's self-regulated cognitive and metacognitive processes while using

computer-based learning environments. *Educational Psychologist*, 45(4), 203-209.

Häkkinen, P., Juntunen, M. Laakkonen, I. 200 . Tulevaisuuden oppimisympäristö yksilölliset ja yhteisölliset oppimisen tilat. Teoksessa . Pohjola (toim.) Uusi koulu. Oppiminen mediakulttuurin aikakaudella. Jyväskylän yliopistokoulutuksen tutkimuslaitos, 51–63.

Ivanova, M. 2010. Design and Development of a Three-Dimensional Personal Learning Space. 5th Plymouth e-Learning Conference, Plymouth, UK, 8–9 April, 2010 <http://www.slideshare.net/malinkaiva/a-view-of-3d-ple>

Kirschner, P. A., Strijbos, J. W., Kreijns, K., & Beers, P. J. (2004). Designing electronic collaborative learning environments. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 52(3), 47-66.

Laakkonen, I. Juntunen, M. 200 . Tulevaisuuden oppimisympäristö Henkilökohtaiset ja avoimet oppimisen tilat. Teoksessa . Viteli A. Östman (toim.) Tuovi 7. Interaktiivinen tekniikka koulutuksessa 2009 -konferenssin tutkijatapaamisen artikkelit. Tampereen yliopisto: Informaatiotutkimuksen ja interaktiivisen media laitosa (INFIM), 69–93.

Laakkonen, I. Taalas, P. 201 . Environnements personnels d'apprentissage et nouvelle culture d'apprentissage, *Recherches et Applications Létran ais dans le Monde No . Gillet* 2013 .

Laakkonen, I. 2011. Uusia oppimisen ympäristöjä rakentamassa. *iel*, koulutus ja yhteiskunta. Kielikoulutuspolitiikan verkoston verkkolehti 4.10.2011.

Laakso, M. (2013) Pelillisuus pedagogisessa toimintakulttuurissa. In Silander, Pasi (Ed.), Johtajuudella toimintakulttuurin muutokseen – tietoyhteiskuntakehitykseen kouluissa ja opetustoimessa, Helsingin kaupungin opetusviraston mediakeskus TOMUT-hanke

Learning Environments: Challenging the dominant design of educational systems. EC- TEL Workshops, Volume 213 von CEUR Workshop Proceedings,

Leone, S. (2013). *Characterisation of a personal learning environment as a lifelong learning tool*. Springer Science & Business Media.

Lubensky, R. 2007. The present and future of Personal Learning Environments (PLE). Robin Good's Master new media blog. June 15, 2007.

Martindale, T. & Dowdy, M. 2010. Personal Learning Environments. Teoksessa G. Velet- sianos (toim.) *Emerging technologies in distance education*. Athabasca University Press, 177–193.

Mattila, P., Brauer, S., Arhippainen, L. & Rantakokko, A. (2013). Towards Immersive User Friendly Future Learning Spaces in Education. In: 3rd European Immersive Education Summit, London, UK, 28- 29 November 2013, 111-122.

Mikroyannidis, A. & Connolly, T. 2012. Introducing Personal Learning Environments to informal learners: Lessons learned from the OpenLearn case study. Teoksessa PLE Conference 2012, 11-13 July 2012, Aveiro, Portugal. <http://oro.open.ac.uk/34501/> National College. (2011). About personalising learning . Nottingham: National College

Narciss, S., Proske, A. & Koerndle, H. (2007). Promoting self-regulated learning in web-based environments. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 23(3), 1126-1144.

NMC Horizon Project Short List: 2012 K-12 Edition OCSE – Organisation for Economic Cooperation Development. (2006). *Schooling for tomorrow: Personalising education*. Paris: Centre for Educational Research and Innovation, OECD.

Olivier, B., & Liber, O. (2001). *Lifelong Learning: The Need for Portable Personal Learning Environments and Supporting Interoperability Standards*. The JISC Centre for Educational Technology Interoperability Standards, Bolton Institute. Retrieved from <http://wiki.cetis.ac.uk/images/6/67/Olivierandliber2001.doc>

Parson, Vanessa & Bignell, Simon (2011) Using problem-based learning within 3D virtual worlds. In Charles Wankel & Randy Hinrichs (Eds.), *Cutting-edge technologies in Higher Education: Transforming Virtual World Learning*. Bradford, GBR: Emerald Insight (Emerald Group) PLE conference portal: <http://mediendidaktik.sharedby.co/share/CetsXB>

Savonia - Personal Learning Environment:
http://portal.savonia.fi/pdf/julkaisutoiminta/SAVONIA_ple_2011_lopullinen_versio.pdf

Rigby, J. 2013. *Review of Pre- commercial Procurement Approaches and Effects on Innovation. Compendium of Evidence on the Effectiveness of Innovation policy Intervention*. Manchester Institute of Innovation Research Manchester Business School, University of Manchester.

Rodríguez Ilera, J. L., Rubio, M. J., Galván, C., & Barberà, E. (2014). Diseño de un entorno mixto e-portfolio/ple centrado en el desarrollo de competencias transversales. *EDUTEC, Revista Electrónica de Tecnología Educativa*, (47).

Sawyer, K. (2006). The new science of learning. In: *The Cambridge handbook of the learning sciences*. Cambridge university press.

Shaikh, Z. A., & Khoja, S. A. (2011). Teachers' Skills set for Personal Learning Environments. In *Proceedings of the 10th European Conference on e-Learning, vols* (Vol. 1, pp. 762-769).

Staker, H. & Horn, M. 2012. *Classifying K-12 Blended learning*. Innosight institute.

Thompson, L. & Fine, G.A. (1999). Socially Shared Cognition, Affect, and Behavior: A Review and Integration. *Personality and Social Psychology Review* 1999, Vol. 3, No. 4, 278-302. <http://psr.sagepub.com/content/3/4/278.full.pdf> UNESCO. (1999). *The world declaration on higher education for the twenty-first century vision and action*. Paris: UNESCO UNESCO Institute for Education. (1999). *Glossary of adult learning in Europe*. Paris: UNESCO.

Wheeler, S. 2009. Anatomy of a PLE. published on a blog: Learning with 'e's 11.7.2010 <http://stevewheeler.blogspot.com/2010/07/anatomy-of-ple.html>

Wilson, S., Liber, O., Johnson, M., Beauvoir, P., Sharples, P. & Milligan, C. D. 2006. *Personal*

Winne, P. H., & Hadwin, A. F. (1998). Studying as self-regulated engagement in learning. In D. Hacker, J. Dunlosky, & A. Graesser (Eds.), *Metacognition in*

Educational Theory and Practice (pp. 277-304). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

Winters, F., Greene, J., & Costich, C. (2008). of learning within computer-based learning environments: A critical analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 20(4), 429-444.

